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Erasmus+ Project

lightcode

Strengthening the Digital
Transformation of Higher Education
Through Low-Code

Work Package 5

LIGHTCODE DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

REACH Innovation

[Version 2.0]

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Erasmus+ Project
lightcode

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INTRODUCTION

The LightCode Erasmus+ Project (Nr.2022-1-FR01-KA220-HED-00086863) aims to make higher education more inclusive, shaping opportunities for all students to develop competitive advantages in digital skills. It focuses on the priority of digital transformation in higher education, in particular for areas where not enough attention is paid to digital skills development and envisages to offer and implement educational material using low-code techniques at cross-sectoral level. The project is based on the development of interconnected higher education systems, as it aims to develop digital skills for all students, regardless of their field of study, in order to make use of their knowledge and expertise in the respective scientific field by exploiting the potential of “low-code”.

The present document describes the adopted *Dissemination Strategy* for the LightCode Erasmus+ Project, based on the project’s goals and using the Dissemination Kit¹ [1] developed by the dissemination project partner REACH Innovation, to fulfill the aims of the project work package WP5. The “LightCode Dissemination Strategy” comprises the following main aspects, which are further described in detail within this document:

- LightCode General Goals & Dissemination Goals.
- LightCode Target Groups.
- LightCode Dissemination Channels.
- LightCode Network Building with Partners’ Collaboration.
- LightCode Sustainable Dissemination Strategy.
- LightCode Dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Targets.

¹ <http://www.lightcode-project.eu/dissemination-kit/>

SECTION 1: LIGHTCODE VISION

Based on the vision of the LightCode project to implement educational material using low-code techniques at cross-sectoral level, developing inter-connected higher education systems, in order foster digital skills for all students, exploiting the potential of the low-code concept, REACH developed a compelling branding that reflects both the aims and target audience of the LightCode Project.

First, the simplicity of the low-code approach to coding is expressed by means of a vivid color palette. Secondly, the imagery invites people not particularly connected to technical coding to explore the low-code approach. Finally, the traditional symbol for coding "</>" is referred to but in a more friendly way.

1.1 Branding embedding LightCode's Vision

The LightCode branding aligns with the project's goals. The code symbol is the basis for the development of the LightCode logo. The logo final version was elaborated considering the feedback provided by the Consortium, via voting of preferred logo option. It combines a modern color palette, with a neon-based design of the code symbol and a bulb for expressing the creative possibilities of the low-code approach. REACH delivered 154 versions (types, formats, colors) to the Consortium (available for downloading in the LightCode Online Repository, [linked here](#)). Some examples can be observed in the LightCode Homepage (link: <http://www.lightcode-project.eu/dissemination-kit/>).

Figure 1: Example of a version of the LightCode Logomark & Full Logotype.

A more detailed explanation of the LightCode branding decisions can be found on the "LightCode Brand Brief" document, produced by REACH [2].

SECTION 2: LIGHTCODE DISSEMINATION GOALS

The LightCode activities that are relevant to the communication and dissemination of the project are dealt within the work package WP5, which the following aims:

- Create awareness about the project and communicate the project activities, events, outcomes, results and achievements to its target groups, as well as to the widest possible audience.
- Target and engage specific audiences and stakeholders who will benefit from the information, results and outputs of the project in order to close the gap in the required digital skills and exploitation of the opportunities offered by the low-code approach.
- Develop, implement and monitor a multi-dimensional communication and dissemination strategy to enhance the visibility of the project.
- Share project results with partner organizations and wider communities and maximize their impact.
- Promote the possibility of transferring and building on the results of the project into existing, new and improved practices that could be integrated into the programs of the partner universities as well as other universities across Europe.

"The actual use of project outcomes depends on successful dissemination activities. It is important to understand that an effective dissemination strategy is the basis for successful exploitation of the project results."

The project results have great potential to be exploited by various universities and thus contribute to closing the gap between the higher education provided in any discipline and the development of digital skills capable of meeting the demands of the labor market due to the constantly increasing digitalization. The wide dissemination of the project results, following the goals listed above, play a paramount role in the project, in order to maximize the impact of the LightCode project via the exploitation of its results.

SECTION 3: LIGHTCODE TARGET GROUPS

The LightCode project is concerned with the topic of "Coding", which is usually linked to a high degree of computer expertise. Therefore, it is understood in an excluding way: only those with such an expertise can have access to the possibilities of coding. Low-code or no-code methods transform this scenario. They give rise to an inclusive understanding of coding, opening the door of coding to people without deep computer knowledge.

The universe of the target audience can be divided in two groups: (1) People with qualified coding knowledge; and (2) People without coding experience neither theoretical knowledge. Although the first group is an important target group, regarding the education about how to teach low code, the most important group is the second one. The LightCode project mainly focuses on people that experience coding from an excluding perspective, inviting them to believe they can also benefit from the potentialities of programming but with low or no technical skills.

The main target groups of stakeholders, who can profit from the developments of the LightCode project, can be divided in the following categories:

1. Students of Universities or High-Education Institutions.
2. Universities and High-Education Institutions' Professors and Faculty Members.
3. Universities and High-Education Institutions' Students' Communities.
4. Local & International Educational Communities and Networks.
5. Local & International IT Communities and Networks.
6. Local, Regional & International Community Members (General Public).
7. 3rd Sector Organizations at Local Level and at EU & International Levels.
8. EU & Erasmus+ related Networks, Communities, and Initiatives.
9. EU & Erasmus+ related Projects & involved Partners.

All the target groups categories listed here will be taken into account within the project's Dissemination Strategy. They might need different ways to have information-contents communicated to them, via the different dissemination channels of the project.

SECTION 4: LIGHTCODE DISSEMINATION CHANNELS

The Disseminations Channels available for the project include: the Project Website; the Social Media accounts defined for the project (in LinkedIn, X (Twitter), Instagram, and Facebook); and the project Platform (to be developed by KarmicSoft). These are the main means for disseminating the project results and especially for bringing about public engagement with the LightCode Erasmus+ Project.

REACH has established all the social media accounts for the LightCode project, as well as the project website, within the platform-channels listed in Table 1.

Channel / Social Media	Site / Account / Link
LightCode Website	LightCode Erasmus+ Project Website http://www.lightcode-project.eu/
LinkedIn	lightcode-erasmus-project https://www.linkedin.com/company/lightcode-erasmus-project/
Twitter	@lightcode_proj https://twitter.com/lightcode_proj/
Instagram	@lightcode_project https://www.instagram.com/lightcode_project/
Facebook	LightCode Erasmus+ Project https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100090357237506
Zenodo	LightCode Project Zenodo Open Science Community https://zenodo.org/communities/lightcode_erasmusplus_project
YouTube	LightCode Erasmus+ Project YouTube Channel https://www.youtube.com/channel/UcJi9SdZ5IzSY_EYDi7LDbyg
LightCode Platform	LightCode Erasmus+ Project Platform <i>(not yet available, status of Dec.2023)</i>

Table 1: LightCode Project – Website & Social Media Accounts.

All LightCode social media accounts are linked in the project's website and REACH, as the dissemination project partner, promotes the project via posts about its main objectives and about its partners, among other project's initial activities. All project partners and collaborators are expected to engage with and to disseminate the LightCode social media accounts, as well as to animate other project interested collaborators to follow the accounts, so that LightCode Erasmus+ Project can gain better visibility, achieve awareness about its goals and ways to reach them, and in consequence grow its network for further exploitation of the project's results.

4.1 LightCode Dissemination within the Website

The [website of the LightCode Erasmus+ Project](#) aims at creating awareness about the content, activities and results of the project. Its scope is an audience as wide as possible, e.g.: project stakeholders, universities, students, general public.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the LightCode Website (Home upper view).

The design of the website relies on the branding previously described. The website was built with the web content management system Wordpress² and has been optimized for users of desktops, laptops and mobile devices (tablets, phones).

² <https://wordpress.org/about/>

The LightCode Website www.lightcode-project.eu sections and sub-sections are listed below:

- 1. Landing Page** (<http://www.lightcode-project.eu/>)
- 2. Project** (<http://www.lightcode-project.eu/project/>)
 - 2.1 Project Management
 - 2.2 LightCode Manifesto
 - 2.3 Teachers Training Programme
 - 2.4 LightCode Course
 - 2.5 LightCode Platform
 - 2.6 Dissemination
- 3. Partners** (<http://www.lightcode-project.eu/partners/>)
 - 3.1 Paris Dauphine University–PSL (Coordinator)
 - 3.2 University of Macedonia
 - 3.3 University of Niš
 - 3.4 Karmic Software Research
 - 3.5 REACH Innovation
 - 3.6 University of Zagreb
 - 3.7 Symplexis
- 4. Resources** (<http://www.lightcode-project.eu/resources/>)
 - 4.1 Dissemination Kit
 - 4.2 Publications
 - 4.3 Linked Resources
- 5. News** (<http://www.lightcode-project.eu/news/>)
- 6. Contact** (<http://www.lightcode-project.eu/contact-2/>)

4.2 LightCode Dissemination within LinkedIn

The LinkedIn account for LightCode aims at networking with stakeholders and the project partners so that the latter can communicate the LightCode's activities to their own networks. See Figure 3.

Figure 3: LinkedIn Account for LightCode (Screenshot featuring the account profile).

Since the creation of the LinkedIn LightCode account, in March 2023, as a public project / company social media account, it has attracted a total of 186 followers, being 70% from the last period of 90 days from the current date (end of the year 2023). A total of 31 posts about the project were published in the LinkedIn account so far, engaging with many of its members, via the used

“#hashtags”³ (see Figure 18), as well as via the project partners’ accounts and their contacts.

4.3 LightCode Dissemination within X (Twitter)

The X (Twitter) account for LightCode targets a broader audience, including people who may have general interests in Erasmus+ projects, as well as in coding development. See Figure 4.

Figure 4: X (Twitter) Account for LightCode (@lightcode_proj).

Since the creation of the LightCode Twitter account in February 2023, it has posted 49 tweets about the project and its partners. Although the statistics of

³ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1n6TdVmCjQjTyu8hcTZMkCtDt5jxG6TDy/view?usp=sharing>

the Twitter platform shows that the LightCode account attracted the attention of many members, so far it gained only 12 followers (up to the end of 2023).

4.4 LightCode Dissemination within Instagram

The LightCode Instagram account (Figure 5) aims at communicating in an informal language the LightCode project to various target groups within the broadest audience possible, particularly focusing on university students, faculty members, and on low-code stakeholders.

Figure 5: LightCode Instagram Account (@lightcode_project).

Since the creation of the LightCode Instagram account in February 2023, it has attracted the attention of 84 followers, with a total of 28 posts about the

project and its partners (status of end of 2023). The engagement within the Instagram account seems to be easier to achieve with the platform's members, counting with the support of the project partners and their contacts, as this social media channel is currently at its best booming phase among younger communities. This also reflects the interest of the students' target group in the project subject.

4.5 LightCode Dissemination within Facebook

The LightCode Facebook account (Figure 6) aims at communicating the LightCode project to various target groups, particularly focusing on Erasmus+ Communities, University students and faculty members, and on low-code stakeholders.

Figure 6: Facebook Account for LightCode Project (Facebook Page ID: 11032145331770).

Since the creation of the LightCode Facebook account as a public educational social media site, in the beginning of March 2023, it has gained attention of 128 followers, has received 94 likes as a page, and it published so far 35 posts about the project and its partners (status of end of 2023). The LightCode Facebook page engages with many Facebook members, with the project partners and their contacts, as well as with members from the Erasmus+ Facebook communities: "Erasmus+ Projects" and "Erasmus+ KA1 & KA2" (both are public groups with more than 200K members).

4.6 LightCode YouTube Channel

Since October, the LightCode Erasmus+ Project counts with a YouTube Channel to reinforce the project's activities. There you can already find the first videos with a message from LightCode partners about the opportunities generated by the project to its end-users. LightCode YouTube Channel Link: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCJi9SdZ5IzSY_EYDi7LDbYg

4.7 LightCode Zenodo Community

The LightCode Zenodo Open Science Community was established in the end of 2023 at the Zenodo.org platform. All public materials and documentation produced by the LightCode project will be included in this community. Link: https://zenodo.org/communities/lightcode_erasmusplus_project

4.8 LightCode Dissemination within the Project Platform

The LightCode project platform is currently under development, within WP3 by project partner KarmicSoft. So far, the platform is not yet available for testing (status Dec.2023). The LightCode Platform will also be an important channel for the dissemination of the project results. It shall be linked in the project website to provide secured networking capabilities.

SECTION 5: LIGHTCODE NETWORK BUILDING

The “Network Building” of the project LightCode happens in a straightforward way, with the Consortium Partners’ collaboration, with the use of all created dissemination materials (Dissemination Kit) and the available communication and dissemination channels.

5.1 Tool-Kit for Network Building

All Dissemination-Kit elements [1], shown in the website page via the menu-command “Resources”⁴, are fundamental for the dissemination and network community building of the project. In this section, more information about the dissemination tool-kit elements are presented.

5.1.1 Project Website & Social Media Channels

All Media Channels of the Dissemination-Kit [1], described in Section 4 previously, play a very important role to enable network building for the project (for detailed information see the sub-sections 4.1 to 4.6 of this document).

Taking the LinkedIn LightCode account as an example, its “Contents Highlights” reports that in the year 2023 the project page received 5344 “Impressions” (see Figure 7), with an overall of 372 page views; 153 unique visitors; and 20 custom button clicks (see Figure 8). This shows the positive effect that LightCode is gaining with its awareness posts so far, as well as with network building on the LinkedIn platform.

⁴ <http://www.lightcode-project.eu/dissemination-kit/>

Metrics

Figure 7: LightCode LinkedIn Impressions Metrics in 2023.

Visitor metrics

Figure 8: LightCode LinkedIn Visitors Metrics in 2023.

5.1.2 Deliverables & Other Project Results Documentation

Based on the LightCode branding and on the usual contents needed in EU project reports as deliverables, REACH designed a Word template for

elaborating the Work Packages reports/deliverables related to the LightCode project. The current document is an example of the use of this template.

The “LightCode Deliverable Template” can be downloaded from the website page via the menu-command “Resources”⁵, or directly via [this link](#). The use of the template for the publications of the project is also important to keep the project branding identity.

5.1.3 LightCode Presentations & Press Release Material

REACH provides a Power Point template for creating presentations about the LightCode Project, for internal meetings and for external presentations, including also press release material, about the project’s results coming from LightCode Work Packages’ developments.

The “LightCode Presentation Template” can be downloaded from the website page via the menu-command “Resources”⁶, or directly via [this link](#). The use of the presentation template for the project’s work packages’ progress presentations is very important to keep the project branding identity, with the required credits for the EU funding and the Erasmus+ project number (See Figure 9). It is expected to be used by all Consortium partners when reporting about the LightCode project in live or virtual presentations.

⁵ <http://www.lightcode-project.eu/dissemination-kit/>

⁶ <http://www.lightcode-project.eu/dissemination-kit/>

Figure 9: Example of the cover slide of the LightCode PowerPoint Presentation Template.

5.1.4 LightCode Newsletters & Leaflet

Based on the same concept of LightCode branding, REACH designed a template for developing the newsletter of the LightCode Project. The Newsletter is planned to be distributed digitally and eventually for printing (if required). The “LightCode Newsletter Template” can be downloaded from the website page via the menu-command “Resources”⁷, or directly via [this link](#).

So far, two Newsletters have been produced by REACH and published in all project’s dissemination channels (see Figure 10), with contributions from all partners about the project’s progress and activities.

⁷ <http://www.lightcode-project.eu/dissemination-kit/>

Figure 10: LightCode Newsletters published in 2023.

The LightCode project's leaflet was finalized and disseminated in April 2023. It provides a brief description of the goals of the project; about the Low-Code concept and its use in the LightCode project; as well as information about the project partners (see Figure 11). The leaflet can be printed, if necessary, for distribution among stakeholders at events.

Figure 11: LightCode Project Leaflet.

The leaflet was designed following the LightCode branding, aiming at offering a direct and engaging message to the main target groups. The leaflet is digitally available, including a printable version (with trimming marks). It can be downloaded from the LightCode website via the menu-command “Resources” for public usage.⁸

⁸ <http://www.lightcode-project.eu/dissemination-kit/>

5.2 Improving Project Dissemination via Networking

It is extremely important that All Project Partners get engaged with the project Dissemination and with its Community Network Building. For bringing this in practice, partners are guided by the project dissemination partner on how to communicate the project's results and activities in an effective way. Specifically, the "what, why, how" methodology shall be used: "What" stands for the activity or result to be communicated itself; "Why" explains its importance; and "How" lists the steps to follow to achieve impact with the communication.

Project partners shall remember that "Information is giving out and Communication is getting through" [3]. They shall also keep in mind the differences that there are between the terms and concepts of "Communication", "Dissemination" and "Exploitation" in a project: *Communication* stands for informing about projects and their results. *Dissemination* stands for describing and making results available for use to a broader audience. Finally, *Exploitation* is concerned with making use of the project results as much and as impactful as possible.

With the above in mind, all project partners shall make sure that the following aspects are being continuously prepared and performed during project lifetime:

- Get the work package dissemination material ready, along its development, and send it to the REACH for posting and post about it individually and/or using your institution's distribution channels.
- Engage with Posts of LightCode Accounts (e.g.: Like, Comment, Replicate, Invite Contacts, Indicate/Recommend to others).
- Send the digital version of LightCode Leaflet to your colleagues.
- Send the digital version of LightCode Newsletter to your contacts!
- Prepare a note about LightCode Project to publish on the local newspaper of your city, or on your School Annual Report!

- Find new LightCode or low code related projects and initiatives to enhance our Network.
- Act and interact! THINK GLOBAL & ACT LOCAL today & everyday!

SECTION 6: LIGHTCODE SUSTAINABLE DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

The Dissemination Strategy for the LightCode is based on the project's overall goals, using the Dissemination Kit already deployed to fulfill the specific dissemination aims defined within WP5. As already presented, together with the dissemination channels, some templates for the LightCode project were elaborated by REACH, to be used all through the project lifetime, when producing Work Packages' Deliverables, Power Point Presentations, and periodic project Newsletters.

Figure 12: LightCode Project Dissemination Strategy Important Factors.

The LightCode Dissemination Strategy is to be followed throughout the project lifetime, including the following tasks and aims:

- Report and promote the results of all the project work packages (WPs).
- Outline the target groups that need to be reached.

- Define the dissemination channels and tools, as well as the responsibilities of partners and instructions for reporting the dissemination activities.
- Promote the project and its outcomes to relevant stakeholders and the general public.
- Raise awareness about the specific objectives of the project and how they will be achieved.
- Disseminate the project results to relevant stakeholders, target group members and decision makers.
- Ensure the sustainability of the project results even after the completion of the project.

6.1 Dissemination Strategy Goals

The seven aspects presented in Figure 13 reflect the general goals of the LightCode Dissemination Strategy.

Figure 13: LightCode Dissemination Strategy General Goals.

In a nutshell, the dissemination will follow the steps illustrated in Figure 14, with the communication, dissemination and networking structure, with the expected interaction among partners and external stakeholders sharing information illustrated via Figure 15.

Figure 14: Dissemination Strategy in a Nutshell.

Figure 15: LightCode Project Dissemination & Networking Structure.

The interaction between all LightCode project partners and the dissemination partner occurs in an intuitive way, taking into account the available information about the project results, all the communication channels defined for the project, as well as the partners' individual activities and networking.

The dissemination contents will be regularly monitored using the Dissemination Calendar (Figure 16), and also via statistics analysis from the social media accounts, in terms of reaches, engagements, followers; as well as qualitatively evaluated after the release of single outcomes (posts; tweets; newsletters; podcasts) with a standard regular interval. Self-evaluation of the project will be continuously carried out to identify gaps or leverage points in the LightCode project's dissemination activities.

SECTION 7: RESULTS MONITORING FOR DISSEMINATION

The monitoring of the work packages (WPs) project results and deliverables for their subsequent dissemination among the target groups of stakeholders is a crucial aspect of the project, playing a significant role in ensuring project success and impact. While dissemination ensures that the project's impact is maximized and knowledge is shared, monitoring deliverables is essential for maintaining control, minimizing risks, and ensuring the project stays on course throughout its lifecycle. Together, these practices contribute to achieving project objectives and maintaining stakeholder confidence in the project team's capabilities. The importance of both aspects related to monitoring and dissemination, rely on some key-factors:

- **Knowledge Sharing:** Dissemination allows the sharing of project outcomes, findings, and knowledge with stakeholders, contributing to the collective understanding of the subject matter.
- **Validation and Recognition:** Sharing results provides a platform for validation by the wider community or relevant stakeholders, reinforcing the credibility of the project. Recognition of achievements enhances the project team's reputation and may attract potential collaborators, funders, or partners for future endeavors.

- **Informed Decision-Making:** Stakeholders, including policymakers, industry professionals, and the general public, can make more informed decisions based on the insights and outcomes generated by the project.
- **Technology Transfer:** Projects often develop new technologies, methodologies, or best practices. Dissemination facilitates the transfer of these innovations to other projects, industries, or communities.
- **Maximizing Impact:** Effective dissemination increases the potential impact of the project by reaching a broader audience, thereby contributing to the project's overall success and the achievement of its objectives.
- **Public Engagement:** Dissemination engages the public and raises awareness about the project's goals, encouraging public interest and support for the initiative.
- **Policy Influence:** Project results can influence policy decisions when shared with policymakers, helping to shape regulations, guidelines, or practices in the relevant field.
- **Feedback and Improvement:** Stakeholder feedback obtained through dissemination channels provides valuable insights for the project team, aiding in refining methodologies, addressing concerns, and improving future iterations or related projects.
- **Project Control:** Monitoring deliverables ensures that the project stays on track and aligns with its original objectives, timelines, and budgetary constraints.
- **Risk Management:** Regular monitoring helps identify potential risks and issues associated with deliverables early in the project lifecycle, allowing for timely corrective actions.
- **Resource Optimization:** Efficient monitoring allows for the optimal allocation of resources, preventing bottlenecks and ensuring that resources are utilized effectively to achieve project milestones.

- **Stakeholder Confidence:** Consistent monitoring and timely delivery of high-quality deliverables build stakeholder confidence in the project team's ability to meet its commitments.
- **Adaptability to Change:** Monitoring facilitates the identification of changes in project requirements, scope, or external factors, enabling the project team to adapt and adjust plans as needed.
- **Quality Assurance:** Monitoring ensures that deliverables meet predefined quality standards, reducing the likelihood of defects, errors, or the need for extensive revisions.
- **Communication and Transparency:** Regular updates on deliverable status promote transparency within the project team and among stakeholders, fostering effective communication and collaboration.
- **End-User Satisfaction:** For projects with external clients, monitoring and delivering on commitments contribute to client satisfaction, potentially leading to positive references or future collaborations.

7.1 Specific LightCode WPs Results Monitoring for Dissemination

The participation of LightCode project partners in the tasks of communicating and disseminating the project is fundamental for the achievement of the key factors listed above and for the success of the project's impact. Partners, together with the project's target groups and stakeholders can help the project achieve higher impact levels, via basic joint-efforts: 1) Leveraging Diverse Networks and involving them in dissemination activities, allowing the project this way to connect with a wider and more varied audience. 2) Enhancing Credibility and legitimacy to the project, by endorsing and participating in dissemination efforts, creating in this way strong trustworthiness and reliability of the project's results and findings. 3) Targeting Specific Audiences and Insights, so that the dissemination can tailor strategies to effectively reach and engage these target groups ensuring that the project's messages are well-received. 4) Multiplying Outreach Efforts, via the implementation of multiplier events for extending the project's visibility beyond what the core team could

achieve independently. 5) Facilitating Two-Way Communication with valuable feedback on dissemination strategies, ensuring they are effective and resonate with the intended audience. 6) Expertise and Resource Sharing to support dissemination activities within a collaborative approach for enhancing the overall quality of the dissemination efforts. 7) Local Knowledge and Expertise about the local community focus. 8) Sustaining Long-Term Impact for ensuring that the partnerships and the impact of dissemination activities can extend beyond the project's duration, via continued sharing of project outcomes even after the project concludes. 9) Increasing Engagement Levels and Building a Supportive Ecosystem via actively engagement with their own networks, fostering a sense of community around the project, as well as via build an ecosystem of universities, organizations, individuals, and communities that are invested in the project's success, fostering a collaborative and mutually beneficial environment. All those collaborative efforts of partners bring diversity, resources, and expertise to the dissemination process, ensuring that the project's messages are effectively communicated and that its outcomes are widely recognized and appreciated.

Overall, REACH will monitor and manage the dissemination of the project results, interacting with the project partners and specifically with the work package leaders, as well as guide the engagement with the project community of stakeholders, by following the calendar of work packages' results illustrated in Figure 16; and with selected awareness dates shown in Figure 18 for the year 2023.

Quantitative Indicators considered for the social media accounts are: Number of Followers (as in Figure 17), Reactions, Engagements and Impressions. With the website the indicators are: Nr. of Visitors and Views: Page views per month, Visits per month, Visits per page, and average duration of individual visits. As can be observed in Figure 17, the project targets for communication via the Social Media channels are, in general, realistic and achievable. Only the final target of the social media Facebook (800 followers) may be difficult to reach.

Figure 16: LightCode Dissemination Calendar.

The LightCode Dissemination Calendar is digitally available and it can be downloaded from the LightCode website via the menu-command “Resources/Publications”, within the list of deliverables of WP5, or directly from [this link](#).

	Status	Month 14 December 2023	KPI – Month 19	KPI – Month 26	KPI-Month 33
X (Twitter)		10/12	20	35	50
	KPI Control /Achievement		Tweets/Posts Engagements, Hashtags		
Instagram		71/84	100	150	200
	KPI Control /Achievement		Posts & Stories engagements, #hashtags & contacts tagging		
LinkedIn		87/186	120	160	200
	KPI Control /Achievement		Posts & Stories engagements, #hashtags , contacts tagging & contact invitation from partners		
Facebook		37/128	200	300	800
	KPI Control /Achievement		Posts & Stories engagements, #hashtags, contacts tagging & contact invitation from partners		

Figure 17: Followers Targets for the LightCode Social Media Channels.

Figure 18: LightCode – Relevant Social Media Awareness Days.

The LightCode related Social Media Awareness Days (2023) document is digitally available and can be downloaded from the LightCode website via the menu-command "Resources/Publications", within the list of deliverables of WP5, or directly from [this link](#).

SECTION 8: DISSEMINATION STRATEGY KPIS & TARGETS

In this section, fit-for-purpose and necessary key performance indicators (KPIs), including realistic targets, are defined to achieve the WP5 goals, complementing this way the sustainable and properly defined "LightCode Dissemination Strategy".

8.1 Specific LightCode Dissemination Objectives and their KPIs

For the purposes of coordinating and harmonizing the networking activities of all the partners, the goals of the networking strategy, the specific

dissemination objectives which were mentioned in Section 2 of this document, were operationalized by REACH.

By developing KPIs and defining which partners are responsible for their fulfillment as well as by creating mechanisms of control, the steps for reaching the goals of the network strategy are clarified. The objectives are outlined and where necessary split into sub-objectives. Each (sub-)objective was made measurable by assigning KPIs to them. Further, control mechanisms were installed to insure the fulfillment of the KPIs.

Objective 1 - O1:

“Create awareness about the project and communicate the project activities, events, outcomes, results and achievements to its target groups, as well as to the widest possible audience.”

O1 shall also cater for providing an effective flow of communication among project partners and its target groups. O1 comprises four sub-goals:

O1.1: Encourage Individual Posts from Partners, also using their native languages, to better engage with local target groups / stakeholders.

O1.2: Enforce that Individual Posts from Partners are communicated to the Dissemination Partner and the whole Consortium as soon as it is published.

O1.3: Enforce that the Dissemination of Results is prepared and sent to the Dissemination Partner when ready.

O1.4: Enforce that the Dissemination of Partners' Events or Activities are prepared and sent to the Dissemination Partner whenever they happen.

For each of sub-goals of O1, realistic and feasible Key-Performance Indicators were planned to be implemented all through the project lifetime, with the support of the Consortium partners, as presented in Table 2.

O1 Sub-Goals KPIs and Control Mechanisms	
O1.1	Encourage Individual Posts in the native languages of Partners.
KPI 1.1	At least <u>1 Post per Month</u> with original material related to the LightCode Project, starting on Month 12, coming from one Consortium Partner.
KPI-Control 1.1	Assignment of Partner/per Month will be guided by REACH and decided by the partners.
O1.2	Enforce that Individual Posts from Partners are communicated.
KPI 1.2	At least <u>1 Post per Month</u> with material that does not necessarily need to be original from partners, re-posting included, coming from any partners.
KPI-Control 1.2	The Dissemination Partner will remind selected partners by the end of each month about this defined goal/activity.
O1.3	Enforce the Dissemination of Results.
KPI 1.3	Results derived from the WPs as defined in the Dissemination Calendar for LightCode.
KPI-Control 1.3	The Dissemination Partner will remind the involved partners by the end of the WP task about their expected result dissemination report.
O1.4	Enforce the Dissemination of Partners' Events and/or Activities.
KPI 1.4	At least <u>4 Events per Year</u> , coming from any partners.
KPI-Control 1.4	The Dissemination Partner will remind ALL partners quarterly of this objective, relating to planned events in the PRs-Calendar.

Table 2: KPIs and. Control Mechanism of O1 Sub-Goals.

Objective 2 – O2:

“Target and engage specific audiences and stakeholders who will benefit from the information, results and outputs of the project in order to close the gap in the required digital skills and exploitation of the opportunities offered by the low-code approach.”

O2 shall provide a high flow of communication for wide dissemination on project results and outputs within the LightCode target groups. It comprises three sub-goals:

02.1: Dissemination of LightCode results via engagements in the Social Media accounts, considering selected and appropriate stakeholders.

02.2: Dissemination via engagements in the Partners' Communities.

02.3: Dissemination via engagements with other correlated Networks and Research Projects.

For each of sub-goals of O2, realistic and feasible Key-Performance Indicators were planned to be implemented all through the project lifetime, with the support of the Consortium partners, as shown in Table 3.

O2 Sub-Goals KPIs and Control Mechanisms	
02.1	Engagements in the Social Media (SM) Accounts
KPI 2.1a	At least 1 Post per Month (including re-posts) in appropriate SM accounts related to the LightCode Project.
KPI 2.1b	Increasing Number of Followers in each Project SM account.
KPI-Control 2.1	The Dissemination Partner will report about the evolution of this objective measurement (KPI) quarterly. Feedback from this observation will connect with the KPI-Controls of the previous Sub-Objectives of O1 (1.1, 1.2, etc...)
02.2	Engagements in the Partners' Communities
KPI 2.2	At least 2 Local Communities-Events per Year, coming from any partners.
KPI-Control 2.2	The Dissemination Partner will remind the partners quarterly of this objective, relating to planned events in the LightCode WPs Dissemination Calendar.
02.3	Engagements with other Networks and Research Projects.
KPI 2.3a	At least 6 Interactions with other Projects per Year, generating at least 6 Posts per Year related to other Networks & Projects (including Re-posts).
KPI 2.3b	At least 6 new Collaborating Networks per Year.
KPI-Control 2.3	The Dissemination Partner will report about the evolution of this objective measurement (KPI) quarterly. Feedback from this observation will connect with the KPI-Controls of the O1 Sub-Objectives.

Table 3: KPIs and. Control Mechanism of O2 Sub-Goals.

Objective 3 – O3:

“Develop, implement and monitor a multi-dimensional communication and dissemination strategy to enhance the visibility of the project.”

O3 shall enforce appropriate and attractive visualization on reported project results and activities, cross-fertilizing the LightCode Network Community. For this to be achieved the following questions will need to be addressed:

How? To be done via the posts that are made graphically, or via images and videos.

Who will provide the data visualization material? The involved partners in the reported action or project result to be disseminated.

When? During or immediately after the action took place / the result is available.

Who will finalize the material for disseminating in the network? The involved partners and the Dissemination Partner will lead the dissemination action.

For O3, realistic and feasible Key-Performance Indicators were planned to be implemented all through the project lifetime, with the support of the Consortium partners, as shown in Table 4.

O3 KPIs and Control Mechanisms	
O3	Visualization on the reported Project Results and Activities
KPI 3	At least 2 visual (graphic) data files per Month, which may relate to actions of the Sub-Objectives of O2, need to be provided by any of the partners of the LightCode Project.
KPI-Control 3	The Dissemination Partner will remind the partners by the end of each month together with the reminders from the Sub-Objectives of O2.

Table 4: KPIs and Control Mechanism of O3.

Objective 4 – O4:

“Share project results with partner organizations and wider communities and maximize their impact.”

O4 shall enforce appropriate promotion of the deliverables and publications produced and stored in the project repository, including via engaging with Open Access Platforms, like with the project’s open-access “LightCode Zenodo Community” account. O4 shall also provide interconnection and active engagement with the Erasmus+ EU Portal, engaging with other related projects and initiatives. O4 comprises the following sub-goals:

O4.1: Communicate every produced deliverable and resource material within the project’s social media accounts with a short explanation, including images and graphs if possible.

O4.2: Directly alert (e.g.: via email or newsletters) the members of the project’s community network that can profit from our deliverables and resources (especially universities and high education organizations).

O4.3: Communicate every resource unit, relevant deliverable and platform features at events and other partners’ activities with project external participants and stakeholders of target groups.

O4.4: Publish results in Open Science / Open Access Platforms.

O4.5: Provide interconnection and active engagement with the Erasmus+ EU Portal, engaging with other related projects and initiatives.

For each of sub-goals of SO 4, realistic and feasible Key-Performance Indicators were planned to be implemented all through the project lifetime, with the support of the Consortium partners, as shown in Table 5.

O4 Sub-Goals KPIs and Control Mechanisms	
O4.1	Communicate on social media channels.

KPI 4.1	Regularly, once a month, until all resources have been featured.
KPI-Control 4.1	The Dissemination Partner will create a list with all the resource units and will constantly update it after being informed by the partners involved in the development when new working files are available in the platform.
O4.2	Communicate within our networks
KPI 4.2	The Dissemination Partner will remind all the partners quarterly to reach out to other institutions.
KPI-Control 4.2	The Dissemination Partner will remind the partners quarterly of this objective, relating to planned events in the Dissem.Calendar.
O4.3	Communicate at events and other partners' activities with project external participants.
KPI 4.3	Results derived from the WPs, at least 6 per year by all partners.
KPI-Control 4.3	The Dissemination Partner will remind all the partners quarterly about this for their upcoming events.
O4.4	Publish results in Open Science / Open Access Platforms.
KPI 4.4	Publish within LightCode Zenodo Open Science Community. At least 6 per year by all partners.
KPI-Control 4.4	The Dissemination Partner will remind ALL partners quarterly of this objective, relating to planned events in the Dissemination Calendar, and will control the material publishing at open science platforms (including Zenodo).
O4.5	Engage with the Erasmus+ EU Portal and other related Projects.
KPI 4.5	At least 2 Networks and 3 Projects per year, coming from any partners. (At least 5 per year by all partners.)
KPI-Control 4.5	The Dissemination Partner will remind ALL partners quarterly of this objective, and will guide the interactions with the Erasmus+ Portal (Project Results Portal).

Table 5: KPIs and Control Mechanism of O4 Sub-Goals.

Objective 5 – O5:

"Promote the possibility of transferring and building on the results of the project into existing, new and improved practices that could be integrated into the programs of the partner universities as well as other universities across Europe."

O5 shall also promote selectively the features, linked apps and spaces available in the Project Platform with partners and other Universities. For O5 to be achieved the following questions will need to be addressed:

How? To be done via the posts, within the project's network, at events and other partners' activities, via Erasmus+ Portal, via open science platforms.

Who will provide the information / material for dissemination? The involved partners in the Platform development and in the project's training.

When? During or Immediately after the information becomes available.

Who will finalize the material for disseminating in the network? The dissemination partner within WP5.

For O5, realistic and feasible Key-Performance Indicators were planned to be implemented all through the project lifetime, with the support of the Consortium partners, as shown in Table 6.

O5 KPIs and Control Mechanisms	
O5	Transferring and building on the results of the project into existing, new and improved practices that could be integrated into the programs of the partner universities practices
KPI 5	Communicate the features and spaces of the platform (regularly - once a month - until all features and spaces have been communicated) with detailed explanation on the dissemination channels (At least 4 per Year – any partner); Directly alert the members of our network and other Universities that may be interested in the platform (At least 6 per year). To be provided by any of the partners of the LightCode Project.
KPI-Control 5	The Dissemination Partner will remind the partners by the end of each month about this Objective and will follow-up its progress.

Table 6: KPIs and Control Mechanism of O5.

CONCLUSIONS

This document described the Dissemination Strategy adopted for the LightCode Erasmus+ Project, using its available Dissemination Kit [1], including the details about how the dissemination task is being carried out within the project, and how the adopted strategy envisages to grow the project's network and to gain more visibility within the main defined target groups in a sustainable way.

The Dissemination Kit together with the Dissemination Strategy build-up a solid structure within the LightCode Erasmus+ Project, to completely fulfill the aims of the Dissemination Work Package WP5, led by REACH, while also achieving major awareness and visibility milestones of the project. This is made possible via the following added values of both Dissemination Kit (*DK*) and Dissemination Strategy (*DS*):

- *DK*: The compelling and attractive LightCode branding, including various Logo options, matching the values of both project and target audience.
- *DK*: The modern and attractive LightCode website, reaching out to the general public and providing the basis for clear project communication about its activities and outcomes.
- *DK*: The social media accounts within major platform-channels (LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram and Facebook), increasing the chances for positive impacts of the project on different audiences, not only within Europe but also Worldwide.
- *DK*: The fit-for-purpose, practical and trendy templates for producing LightCode developments' reports/deliverables; presentations; and newsletters.
- *DS*: The well-planned network building with the partners' collaboration, attending the LightCode general dissemination goals.
- *DS*: The carefully planned way to make the LightCode project's awareness and dissemination for the various defined target groups, via the proper use of the all available tool-kit of materials and dissemination channels, including the project platform to be developed.

- *DS*: The sustainability of the properly defined “LightCode Dissemination Strategy”, fit-for-purpose to achieve the WP5 goals, via and necessary key performance indicators (KPIs) and realistic targets.

"The Dissemination Strategy empowers the collaborative task of disseminating the project's activities and results, relying on the efforts; the participation; the information input; the commitment; and the engagement of all project partners. This way, successful and positive impacts on the target groups can be realistically estimated and expected." (REACH Innovation, 2023)

REFERENCES

1. LightCode Erasmus+ Project (Nr.2022-1-FR01-KA220-HED-00086863): "WP5 – LightCode Dissemination Kit", produced by REACH Innovation, Austria, June 2023. Direct Link: <https://shorturl.at/oQW26>.
2. LightCode Erasmus+ Project (Nr.2022-1-FR01-KA220-HED-00086863): "LightCode Brand Brief - Dissemination" updated version 2.0, produced by REACH Innovation, Austria, December 2023. Link: https://drive.google.com/file/d/15umyirzF9owM-ZhL73FTzxMyNSb-I0yK/view?usp=drive_link.
3. European Commission (Directorate General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture) and the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA): "How to Communicate your Project", Team of Authors: Angelo Strano; Jessica Mariani; Ana Alhoud; Natascha Kittler. First edition: Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2021.